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Editorial

Conscious of Our Consciousness

What is consciousness? How far is it unique to human beings? What does modern science say about it? These are some of the perennial questions that humans have been asking themselves.

Two scientific studies are pertinent in this area. In one of the studies, it is suggested that consciousness arises as an emergent property of the human mind. Yet basic questions about the precise timing, location and dynamics of the neural event(s) allowing conscious access to information are not clearly and unequivocally determined.

Some neuroscientists have even argued that consciousness may arise from a single “seat” in the brain, though the prevailing idea attributes a more global network property (Public Library of Science, 2009).

Do the neural correlates of consciousness correspond to late or early brain events following perception? Do they necessarily involve coherent activity across different regions of the brain,

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or can they be restricted to local patterns of reverberating activity?

A paper suggests that four specific, separate processes combine as a “signature” of conscious activity. By studying the neural activity of people who are presented with two different types of stimuli – one which could be perceived consciously, and one which could not – Dr Gaillard of INSERM and colleagues, show that these four processes occur only in the former, conscious perception task (Public Library of Science, 2009).

This new work addresses the neural correlates of consciousness at an unprecedented resolution, using intracerebral electrophysiological recordings of neural activity. These challenging experiments were possible because patients with epilepsy who were already undergoing medical procedures requiring implantation of recording electrodes agreed to participate in the study. The authors presented them with visually masked and unmasked printed words, then measured the changes in their brain activity and the level of awareness of seeing the words. This method offers a unique opportunity to measure neural correlates of conscious access with optimal spatial and temporal resolutions. When comparing neural activity elicited by masked and unmasked words, they could isolate four converging and complementary electrophysiological markers characterizing conscious access 300 ms after word perception.

All of these measures may provide distinct glimpses into the same distributed state of long-distance reverberation. Indeed, it seems to be the convergence of these measures in a late time window (after 300 ms), rather than the mere presence of any single one of them, which best characterizes conscious trials. “The present work suggests

that rather than hoping for a putative unique marker – the neural correlate of consciousness – a more mature view of conscious processing should consider that it relates to a brain-scale distributed pattern of coherent brain activation,” explained neuroscientist Lionel Naccache, one of the authors of the paper.

Further, in another study, some other scientists propose a new way of understanding how the brain processes unconscious information into our consciousness. According to the model, consciousness arises only in time intervals of up to 400 milliseconds, with gaps of unconsciousness in between (Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne. (2016).

The driver ahead suddenly stops, and you find yourself stomping on your brakes before you even realize what is going on. We would call this a reflex, but the underlying reality is much more complex, forming a debate that goes back centuries: Is consciousness a constant, uninterrupted stream or a series of discrete bits – like the 24 frames-per-second of a movie reel? Scientists from Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPF) and the universities of Ulm and Zurich, put forward a new model of how the brain processes unconscious information, suggesting that consciousness arises only in intervals up to 400 milliseconds, with no consciousness in between.

Continuous or Discrete?

Consciousness seems to work as a continuous stream: one image or sound or smell or touch smoothly follows the other, providing us with a continuous image of the world around us. As far as we are concerned, it seems that sensory information is continuously translated into conscious perception: we see objects move smoothly, we hear sounds continuously, and we smell and feel without interruption. However, another school of thought argues that our brain collects sensory information

only at discrete time-points, like a camera taking snapshots. Even though there is a growing body of evidence against “continuous” consciousness, it also looks like that the “discrete” theory of snapshots is too simple to be true.

A Two-Stage Model

Michael Herzog at EPFL, working with Frank Scharnowski at the University of Zurich, have now developed a new paradigm, or “conceptual framework,” of how consciousness might really work. They did this by reviewing data from previously published psychological and behavioural experiments that aim to determine if consciousness is continuous or discrete. Such experiments can involve showing a person two images in rapid succession and asking them to distinguish between them while monitoring their brain activity.

The new model proposes a two-stage processing of information. First comes the unconscious stage: The brain processes specific features of objects, e.g. colour or shape, and analyzes them quasi-continuously and unconsciously with a very high time resolution. However, the model suggests that there is no perception of time during this unconscious processing. Even time features, such as duration or colour change, are not perceived during this period. Instead, the brain represents its duration as a kind of “number,” just as it does for colour and shape.

Then comes the conscious stage: Unconscious processing is completed, and the brain simultaneously renders all the features conscious. This produces the final “picture,” which the brain finally presents to our consciousness, making us aware of the stimulus.

The whole process, from stimulus to conscious perception, can last up to 400 milliseconds, which is a considerable delay from a physiological point of view. “The reason is that the brain wants to give you the best, clearest information it can, and this demands a substantial amount of time,” explains Michael Herzog. “There is no advantage in making you aware of its unconscious processing because that would be immensely confusing.” This model focuses on visual perception, but the time delay might be different for other sensory information, e.g. auditory or olfactory (Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne. 2016).

This is the first two-stage model of how consciousness arises, and it provides a more complete picture of how the brain manages consciousness than the “continuous versus discrete” debate envisages. But it especially provides useful insights into the way the brain processes time and relates it to our perception of the world.

Three of the articles in this issue explores this topic of consciousness, understanding and experience. The other related articles deal with suffering and death. May we understand ourselves, our self-identity and our self-consciousness!

The Editor

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Desire/Taste and the Worlds of the Internet

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Abstract: Epistemology, the study of knowledge, takes us from the sensible to the intelligible. Epithymics, the study of desire, takes us from the intelligible to the sensible. We have already moved to the sensible through the intelligible content in the worlds of the internet. This is why we need to keep our natural habit for epistemology under erasure and examine our tendency of epithymia (desire). So the author attempts to understand the dynamics of taste and applies these dynamics to the worlds of the internet. The author holds that the key is understanding and addressing our desire. It is in the manner we will have mastery over the epithymics that we will be either enslaved or work our freedom in the worlds of our internet.

Keywords: Epistemology, Epithymics, Worlds of Internet, Taste, Desire, Economimesis

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How can we relate taste to desire? How do we look at the world of the internet using the category of Epithymics (desire), which Derrida uses? Based on Derrida's science of taste and desire, we want to look into the dynamics of desire, so that we will not be enslaved by the worlds of the internet. This diagnostic study is explorative and empowering.

Taste and Desire

If thinking is a form of writing as Jacques Derrida would like us to believe then we have been thinking with our eyes. All thinking has been visual-centric. We have already seen how Derrida tried to shift the centre of gravity of our thinking to our sense of smell and taste away from eyes and ear. This is why he also tried to replace stable episteme with volatile epithymia (desire). Therefore, we can see that epistemology is displaced by epithymics in his work. Epistemology takes us from the sensible to the intelligible. Epithymics takes us from the intelligible to the sensible. We have already moved to the sensible through the intelligible content in

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Epithymics takes us from the intelligible to the sensible. We have already moved to the sensible through the intelligible content in the worlds of the internet. This is why we need to keep our natural habit for epistemology under erasure and examine our tendency of epithymia (desire).

the worlds of the internet. This is why we need to keep our natural habit for epistemology under erasure and examine our tendency of epithymia (desire). To do this, we have to understand the dynamics of taste. The locus of taste is the tongue that performs the functions of speaking and eating. To overcome the privileging of the speech, Derrida finds the site of tongue/ mouth as important as it is also the site of food. He teaches that it is the sounds that one makes while chewing and eating one's food that develops the

sounds of the speech of our language. But the taste is also governed by the sense of smell. Hence, Derrida finds taste as the basic unit of epithymics, the study of desire. Taste does help him to bridge the forced separation of the intelligible and the sensible.

Taste includes the range of distastes and disgusts. Tastes thus embrace desire in its diverse forms. Desire is studied attentively in psychoanalysis. This is why Derrida tilts to the psychoanalytic work of Nicholas Abraham. Psychoanalysis does teach us how we epithymize in our quest to satisfy our tastes and distastes. This drawing ourselves into the dynamics of epithymics can open us to the way we produce our self. We become ourselves through mimesis. But we do not just desire to imitate the other. Our desire is mimetic. It tries to imitate the enjoyment of the other. This is why mimetic desire can be studied by examining economimesis. Economimesis shows that we do not desire to imitate the product but we desire to imitate the process of generating and enjoying the product.

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Non-Logocentric Epithymics

Therefore, how we epithymize is conditioned by the models of enjoyment that we desire to imitate. We become what we are by carrying the trace of what we are not. This is why perhaps Jacques Lacan teaches us that unconscious is the

discourse of the other. Hence, we may have to agree that it is important to study how mimetic desire compels us to become subjects of networks in the worlds of the internet (Trubek, 2008).

The intensities of desire can only be studied by epithymics and not by epistemology. The science of epithymics founded by Derrida is an important tool to understand us and our entanglements on the internet. We are decomposing and recomposing the writings/ texts of the internet. We seem to be enjoying a collage of networks. The collage is dynamic and is not logocentric since none of its constituting elements/ items is simultaneously present. But like the signature which constitute itself as a trace and lingers beyond the author, the dynamic trace of each of the constituent of a collage lingers on as the self of the network goes on a hunt to satisfy its desire in the worlds generated by the internet. The internet can only disseminate. It can only scatter its writings. It is for the self of the network to assemble it into a collage. This is why I call the internet an asemitic semiology. The self of the network assembles a kind of self-serving semiology. We need to take into account this self-serving dimension of the assemblage affected by the self of the network because it can enable us to understand how groups of individuals can epithymize/ pursue their tastes and get locked into an echo-chambers. Such internet bubbles flourish and often come crushing down.

The internet being non-dialectical can only allow the production of the allosomes / the other contents side by side. This condition of the internet perhaps does not allow synthesis and numbs our memory which becomes the reason why we may keep monkeying from one site to the on the internet.

The digital world is non-dialectical. It generates signification by dissemination.

There is no unity of content. Everything stays dissolved in a non-

logocentric absence until the subject of the internet googles or uses other search engines (Dobson Robards & Carah, 2018). Big data analytics attempts to study these taste of the individual and groups and try to engineer and manipulate the minds of the subjects of the network to hop towards their products. It is only when the subject of the network googles that the non-logocentric internet world is generated. But this world is dependent on the interest of the subject of the network which is visible in the pursuits of his/ her tastes. This is why the non-logocentric world of the internet that is dissolving and threatening to break apart has its life through the epithymics of its users.

Conclusion

Hence, we have to understand how tastes are being generated and maintained to keep the subjects hooked to the world of the internet. The internet being non-dialectical can only allow the production of the allosomes / the other contents side by side. This condition of the internet perhaps does not allow synthesis and numbs our memory which becomes the reason why we may keep monkeying from one site to the on the internet. So far our study has mainly been diagnostic. I found the work of Derrida, particularly his *Of Grammatology* (Derrida, 2016) as having great potency to study the dynamic world of the internet and what it does to us. The key is in addressing of our desire. It is in the manner we will have mastery over the epithymics that we will be either enslaved or work our freedom in the worlds of our internet.

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The State of Being Aware: An Introductory Study of Human Consciousness

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Abstract: Consciousness is a common term consciously being used by all but it is very difficult to understand it. Consciousness is the fundamental principle of human life and existence. The understanding of consciousness keeps evolving day by day. Consciousness is being defined by very many theories from different perspectives. Here in this article, there is some basic information to have little knowledge of what is consciousness. When we delve into the concept of consciousness, we have the nature of consciousness, theories of consciousness, levels of consciousness and stages of consciousness. All these things combine together to give us basic knowledge about what is consciousness. As a whole, the main idea of many theories says that human consciousness is the state of being aware and responsive to one's surroundings.

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Keywords: Awareness, Knowing the Other, Environment, Consciousness

Introduction

Consciousness is everything that we come across in our daily life. It is the tune or a melody that stuck in our head, the sweetness of candy which we taste, the love of our parents, the touch of the wind and everything that we feel and experience. It is the fundamental principle of human life and existence. The understanding of human consciousness has been changed from time to time. Once psychology was considered as the study of consciousness but later it is considered as the study of behaviours. The discovery of the quantum nature of our universe changed the course of human history. This quantum theory demands a revision of the role of consciousness as the underlying principle of the universe. There are different ways of understanding consciousness and there are different views according to the cultures and ethnic group. This thesis is a brief summary of what is human consciousness and how we can approach it.

Consciousness is everything that we come across in our daily life. It is the tune or a melody that stuck in our head, the sweetness of candy which we taste, love of our parents, the touch of the wind and everything that we feel and experience. It is the fundamental principle of the human life and existence.

Meanings

Consciousness in common defined as the awareness of the mind about its own process in the current scientific psychology. The majority of scholars accept consciousness as an understanding of the relationship to the objective world which is described by

science. Emotions are central to narrative because they are the principal processes in which selfhood is constructed (Ramana, 2014).

According to the Chambers 21st Century Dictionary, the term consciousness means the state of being aware physically and mentally of one's environment and being awake fully with thoughts and feelings (Robinson, 1997).

According to the Webster Comprehensive Dictionary, it means the power of self-knowledge or internal perception and any form of intellectual activity or its product in direct and convincing knowledge of external or internal objects (Marckwardt, 1998).

Theories of Consciousness

Consciousness is considered to be the mental experiences of every kind therefore it can be taken as the core matter of the study of psychology and psychology is frequently defined as the study of self-consciousness. There are many theories that tries to explain consciousness from different aspects. Some of the theories that have been given by physiologists and psychologists are found here.

One theory says that each atom of the physical body of a human has the attributes of consciousness but the theory was not able to prove by the experiments.

The second theory tried to prove that some special nerves in the human brain are the causes for consciousness. But the fact is that there no such special system for the production of consciousness.

The third theory explains that consciousness is the product of the impulses of the simple nerve cell stimulations or from the identical nerve cells (Gravin, 1949).

a. Metaphysical Theories of Consciousness

The universal metaphysical theories offer replies to the conscious type of the mind and body problem, the ontological position of consciousness relative to the world of physical reality. The existing responses basically equal the standard of mind and body selections together with the main kinds of dualism and physicalism (Penfield, 1978).

Dualist theories regard at least some aspects of consciousness as falling outside the realm of the physical, but specific forms of dualism differ in just which aspects those are substance dualism, property dualism, fundamental property dualism, emergent property dualism, natural monist property.

b. Dualist Theories

Dualist theories regard at least some aspects of consciousness as falling outside the realm of the physical, but specific forms of dualism differ in just which aspects those are substance dualism, property dualism, fundamental property dualism, emergent property dualism, natural monist property. These arguments have been in favour of dualist and other anti-physicalist theories of consciousness (Penfield, 1978).

c. The Self-Representational Theory of Consciousness

Consciousness arises from a particular type of information processing that is familiar from the early days of discoveries and inventions. Self-representational theory of consciousness is one

of the approaches to consciousness that has a rich tradition but has very recently regained a modest degree of popularity among researchers. According to this view, mental states are conscious only when they represent their own occurrence in the right way. A person's experience of the blue sky represents both the sky and itself it is in virtue of representing itself that it is a conscious experience. Franz Brentano, the eminent German philosopher, held that every conscious state is internally directed at two things. It is primarily directed at whatever object it is about and secondarily directed at itself. The bluish sky of our experience is directed primarily at the sky and secondarily directed to itself. Therefore, a conscious state has two representational contents are other-directed content and self-directed content.

Conscious as Self-consciousness

The procedure is from consciousness. All consciousness is self-consciousness. I am the consciousness of others only in being conscious of myself. What is enlightened in me only illuminate others. One must know the level of his own knowledge. Human is conscious because he knows other things and through that, he knows himself. It the same as self-awareness in other words which make a human know that he exists. Human is the symbol of the unity and self-consistency of the reality itself (Chethimattam, 1971).

Consciousness is not a process in the brain but a kind of behaviour though it is controlled by brain like any other behaviour. The understanding of human consciousness is the most difficult and complex thing in the scientific field.

Nature of Human Consciousness

Consciousness is not a process in the brain but a kind of behaviour though it is controlled by the brain like any other behaviour. The understanding of human consciousness is the most difficult and complex thing in the scientific field. Perhaps no other problem has proven more tough to both the philosophical and scientific scholars than an account of the nature of consciousness. The reflective nature of consciousness and its ability to consider itself, to provide a sense of being has led some philosophers to assume that it characterizes the very essence of what it means to be human. It is *Cogito ergo sum* in the words of Descartes. This is not the only meaning but one among many meanings that have come to characterize the nature of consciousness in the present times. Modern psychological views of the nature of consciousness originated from “Principals of Psychology” the classical work of William James which was published in 1890. But it has evolved and developed by many philosophers and mystics from early centuries in many ancient cultures and which could be easily seen and appreciated in Indian tradition. *Sankara* and particularly *Ramanuja* are the main persons who dealt with the nature of consciousness as a point of view for evaluating the reality of the world with details. Their basic suppositions and principles give us more than enough sources to construct a metaphysical nature from the consciousness which is distinct from the objective analysis which has been the traditional procedure of the western perspective (Chethimattam, 1971).

Forms of Human Consciousness

The word Consciousness has a huge and different set of meanings. We may have various highly complex mental activities in our mind when we think of consciousness, such as reflective self-consciousness or introspective consciousness

which is only for human beings. Sometimes we may think of something purely phenomenal and something simple and unitary. The examples of consciousness are the perceptual states of seeing and hearing, but the nature of the consciousness actually more complex and far away from clear understanding (Pandikattu, 1998). The realm of consciousness is hardly tired and known by reflective or introspective forms. There are many different forms of consciousness and there is a vital harmony to all these different forms of consciousness. It is distinctive for its subjectivity or one's own perspective. The huge variety in the forms of consciousness makes the problem very complex in understanding the only conscious subject which has direct access to the way of being focus on the nature of the subjectivity and of forms (Zelazo, 2007).

Levels of Human Consciousness

The enlightening and self-manifesting aspects of consciousness are present at various levels in the actual state of soul and body in human. External understanding reminds the intellectual expression in physical categories of substance, action, attributes, relation. It constitutes another level on which the mind moulds logical categories corresponding to things. Psychic experience of thought, action and limitation indicates a deeper level of empirical consciousness. These empirical levels do not mean a mere passive reception of forms from things. Even on the level of sense experience, the conscious understanding is a constriction of the object. However, this consciousness appears in its more friendly condition in the transcendental realization of being, truth and goodness in things. These present less of an obstacle to the self-expression of the subject and approximate to the native condition of consciousness itself (Chethimattam, 1971).

Stages of Human Consciousness

It is quite easy for any human being to bring the boundaries of our thinking and also those of our consciousness into the realm of experience. This may be done in a different way such as asking some questions or rather each attempt to answer those questions raised. The first half of Rudolf Steiner's philosophical work on freedom deals with a stage of consciousness that may be characterized by the fact that the contents of this stage are given through observation. Exclusively this field of consciousness is most appropriate for the observation of thinking or even more precisely, the philosophy of freedom is not the process itself but as in the ordinary usage of the word and the result of this process as it enters consciousness (Kuhlewind, 1973).

I am, moreover, in the same position when I enter into the exceptional state and reflect on my own thinking. I can never observe my present thinking; I can only subsequently take my experience of my present thinking process as the object of fresh thinking. If I wanted to watch my present thinking, I should have to split myself into two persons, one to think, the other to observe the thinking. But this I cannot do. I can only accomplish it in two separate acts. The thinking to be observed is never that in which I am actually engaged. There are two things which are incompatible with one another: active production and its objective contemplation (Kuhlewind, 1973).

The human consciousness soul delivers the opportunity for human independence. This is confirmed, for instance, by the very fact that we can pose the question of freedom, which would be impossible if we were completely unfree. The potential for freedom is inherent in the consciousness soul insofar as it can observe its own past thinking. This past does not compel directly which is a dead world. The observing authority is

always present but always enters consciousness only afterwards. Ordinary consciousness thinking is a phenomenon whose sources and origin lie before the thinking consciousness (Kuhlewind, 1973).

Conclusion

This brief study on knowing what is human consciousness will likely require theories of many types. These theories are very much helpful to understand the human consciousness better and accept a diversity of models that each in their own way without much contradiction. There is unlikely to be any single theoretical perspective that proves the

There is unlikely to be any single theoretical perspective that proves the only meaning of what is human consciousness but it has evolution in its understanding and has a lot of different meanings and theories which give understanding.

only meaning of what is human consciousness but it has evolved in its understanding and has a lot of different meanings and theories which give understanding. But as a whole, the main idea of many theories says that human consciousness is the state of being aware and responsive to one's surroundings.

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Understanding Understanding and Non-Understanding: The Problems and Possibilities

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Abstract: Life is not limited to the coordinated functioning of millions of cells that make an individual or to one's struggle for survival. It's also about our pursuit to reach the Ultimate or the Absolute in Hegel's terms. In his search for the absolute, he too yearned for someone who would truly understand him. However, it dawns on him, too late though, and says, "Only one man ever understood me, and he didn't understand me". This essay tries to show how "I" expect someone to understand "me" when that "someone" is actually looking at "me" through a very limited understanding of him/herself. Can anyone really have an absolute, objective understanding of me? On the other hand, how much do I understand my own "self" to expect the same from another? Together let us explore and dissect various aspects of

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understanding and how it all comes together in building the relationship. Though we may keep searching for the absolute, it may not be an “absolute” necessity for our everyday living.

Keywords: Hegel, Idealism, Realism, Absolute, Understanding Self and Other

Introduction

Human life is not a solitary journey. We need a companion either to share our thoughts, our life or just for the sake of a human presence. This leads to a relationship and the basis of any relationship is mutual understanding. Most often our life is defined by this pursuit to find that one person with whom we can be truly our “self”.

How much of my “self” do I actually understand? And if at all I do, can I really expect someone else to look at me “objectively” keeping aside the lens of his/ her understanding of him/ herself, through which one often tends to look at the world. The absolute is unattainable and so it is futile to ever expect it, but understanding is the basis of a human relationship.

Being social animals, we naturally get into relationships. A son wants to be understood by his father. A friend expects likewise from his friend. Basically, all of us want to be sure of the other

Understanding and Hegel

Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel (1770-1831), a German philosopher, was an idealist who wanted to put together all the

great works of his predecessors into a single work. Thus, for him, understanding meant reaching the absolute. His life journey was the search for this absolute (Aftab 2008). Apparently, at his death bed, he said, “Only one man ever understood me, and he didn’t understand me” (Davies 1996). It is speculated that Hegel realized that even his close friend probably failed to understand his ideas completely. However, it could also be interpreted that the man whom Hegel refers to, is himself, as he realized that one cannot truly understand oneself or reach the absolute.

Apparently at his death bed Hegel said, “Only one man ever understood me, and he didn’t understand me” For him understanding meant reaching the absolute. His life journey was the search of this absolute. It could also be interpreted that the man whom Hegel refers to, is himself, as he realized that one cannot truly understand oneself or reach the absolute.

Understanding and Non-understanding

Being social animals, we naturally get into relationships. A son wants to be understood by his father. A friend expects likewise from his friend. Basically, all of us want to be sure of the other understanding us. That is to say that, we want to be on the same page when it comes to knowing each other. Jesus says in Mt 7:5, “...first take the log out of your own eye, and then you will see clearly ...”. This verse is often seen in the light of judging others.

But I think Jesus is asking us to first look into our “self”, to know and to understand our “self” - deeper and better. Our

vision is often coloured by “our” perceptions which is embedded deep within and is seldom known to us. Thus, psychologists would say that what we see in others is often a projection of our “self” and not the person who s/he is. We behave or act in a certain way when faced with certain situations. And this behaviour is engineered within our “self”, so much so, that we are often unaware of it. There would be layers of such behaviours which keep happening as a ritual without our knowledge. Only when we understand this behaviour, can we reach the absolute “self”. This ultimate end is when we can genuinely say “I know myself”. Only then we can look at the “other” objectively.

a. Problems

“You don’t understand me!” is a common excuse when any relationship is on the verge of breaking. If person A complains that B doesn’t understand A, then in the context of understanding “the self” we can say that probably A doesn’t understand his/her own “self” and ends up blaming B for the failure of the relationship. Also, A may be seeing only a small part of “the absolute A” while B is seeing another part of this “absolute A”, which A may not have known or doesn’t want to accept at all. Moreover, B could be actually seeing A, coloured in some part of “B”, without even knowing it.

“You don’t understand me!” is a common excuse when any relationship is on the verge of breaking. If person A complains that B doesn’t understand A, then in the context of understanding “the self” we can say that, probably A doesn’t understand his/her own “self” and ends up blaming B for the failure of the relationship.

This is one way of understanding non-understanding. There

could be myriads of such permutations and combinations of understandings. More so, if we take into account the false images we might have of ourselves. None of us is immune to this trap of misunderstanding, except for the very few enlightened ones who can stay still even in the fiercest storms of life.

b. Possibilities

From an objective point of view, I completely agree with Hegel, not out of despair that nobody understands me, but with a clearer understanding that I am a complex being and it is a task in itself first to know and accept myself, and then to even expect someone else, who also understands him/ herself, to understand me. This is the difference between idealism and realism. However, it doesn't mean that we can never have any understanding of the other. We still get into healthy and lifelong relationships without completely understanding each other and accepting each other knowing that the absolute is impossible. In the present world scenario, where our relations are strained, thanks to all the distractions like social media, consumerist attitude etc., it is even more difficult to reach the absolute. It is not a surprise that psychiatric diseases are on the rise because we have lost sight of ourselves and our neighbours. Often people struggle in loneliness and depression, even ending

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their life (Tiwari 2013). In despair we often hear people complaining, “nobody understands me”.

Conclusion

The character Atticus in *To Kill a Mockingbird*, says, “You never really understand a person until you consider things from his point of view... until you climb inside of his skin and walk around it” (Lee, 2006). This leads to empathy. This is probably the absolute that Hegel is referring to. However, to reach this absolute of understanding the other you have to go through a

“You never really understand a person until you consider things from his point of view... until you climb inside of his skin and walk around it” (Lee, 2006)

never-ending task of understanding your own “self”. This is better said than done. Although this might seem depressing, we need not be bogged down because we can still live a very happy life by accepting each other, knowing that absolute understanding may never happen.

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Tuesdays with Morrie: The Meaning of Living and Dying

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Abstract: *Tuesday with Morrie* is a book about living and dying. This book mostly emphasizes the practicality of life, existential realities of life. Morrie, being a Sociology professor addressed to his students on love, acceptance, forgiveness, open communication, death, culture, marriage, regret and many other existential realities with his personal experience and conviction. After having analysed this book, the author explores the basic insights of Morrie, offers his critical reflection, evaluation and situating it into the present scenario.

Keywords: Tuesdays with Morrie, Mitch Albom, Love, Compassion, Culture, Regret, Forgiveness, Humour, Dignity, Courageousness, Interconnectedness

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Introduction

The book *Tuesdays with Morrie* is the final lesson between a college professor Morrie, and one of his long-lost students and the author of the book, Mitch Albom. After seeing his professor in an interview on the show “Nightline,” Mitch Albom is reminded of a promise he made sixteen years ago to keep in touch with him. Now stricken with Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS), Morrie does not have much time left, and Mitch recognizes this fact. ALS is a progressive nervous system disease that affects nerve cells in the brain and spinal cord, causing loss of muscle control. ALS is often called Lou Gehrig’s disease, after the baseball player who was diagnosed with it. The famous physicist Stephen Hawking was also stricken by it.

Albom travels from Michigan to Massachusetts to meet with him. This meeting goes well and affects Mitch and Morrie so much that they meet for the next fourteen consecutive Tuesdays, up until Morrie passes away. During each of these meetings, they discuss a different topic about life. These topics make up the content of the book and include death, love, culture, marriage, regret and the world we live in, among many others.

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The Characters Morrie and Albom

“Morrie” S. Schwartz was born on December 20, 1916, and died on November 4, 1995. He was an American professor

of sociology at Brandeis University. He was a good professor and author. He was the subject of the best-selling book *Tuesdays with Morrie*, written by Mitch Albom, a former student of Schwartz.

Mitch Albom was born in New Jersey in 1958, the second of three children. He grew up loving music and taught himself how to play the piano. He played in bands throughout his teenage years. Albom finished high school in three years and then attended Brandeis University in Waltham, Massachusetts, where he majored in Sociology. After graduation, he continued to explore the world and his love of music, performing in Europe and the United States. However, while living in New

Morrie was more positive in his word and deeds especially in his thinking.

Therefore, he refused to be depressed.

Instead, Morrie had become a lightning rod of ideas. He jotted down his thoughts on yellow pads, envelopes, folders, scrap paper.

York in his 20s, Albom became interested in journalism and volunteered for a local weekly paper, *The Queens Tribune*. This experience piqued his interest in the craft, so he applied to graduate school. Albom earned a Master's degree from Columbia University's graduate school of Journalism followed by an MBA from Columbia University's graduate school of Business. Albom paid part of his tuition by working as a professional pianist. Following his academic career, Albom became a full-time writer in New York City. Albom soon branched out into multiple forms of media, contributing to radio shows and television programs in addition to a growing list of periodicals. Albom is the author of four novels. Three of them have been turned into TV movies, including *Tuesdays with Morrie*, which Oprah Winfrey produced.

Some Basic Insights of Morrie

In this section, I like to highlight some of the basic insights garnered from this insightful book.

“Accept what you are able to do and what you are not able to do”

In March 1995, Morrie was in a wheelchair and his legs dead and he would not walk again. This is the worst condition. But, he was not the person who would worry about the pathetic physical condition. Morrie was more positive in his word and deeds, especially in his thinking. Therefore, he refused to be depressed. Instead, Morrie had become a lightning rod of ideas. He jotted down his thoughts on yellow pads, envelopes, folders, scrap paper. *He wrote bite-sized philosophies about living with death's shadow: “Accept what you are able to do and what you are not able to do”; “Accept the past as past, without denying it or discarding it” (Album, 1997: 10)*

Life with dignity, courage, humour

Morrie at his final stage said that I am at the withdrawal of my life. “Am I going to withdraw from the world, as most people do, or am I going to live?” I decided I’m going to live – or at least try to live – the way I want, with dignity, with courage, with humour, with composure. This show how righteous he is? His words expose the thinking that

“Am I going to withdraw from the world, like most people do, or am I going to live?” I decided I’m going to live-or at least try to live the way I want, with dignity, with courage, with humor, with composure.

nowhere in life he should become problematic to others. He wished that there should be dignity with courage and humour.

Trace out the purpose and live it successfully

Morrie speaks with Albom about finding your true purpose and meaning in life. “So many people walk around with a meaningless life. They seem half-asleep, strayed and blind without motivation. The best way one can trace out the meaning into your life is to devote and dedicate yourself to loving others, devote and dedicate yourself to your community around you, and devote and dedicate yourself to creating something that gives you purpose and meaning.” Instead of accumulating more wealth and more consumption of material goods focus on the things that meaningful and matters a lot. When we shift our attention away from superficial activities and thoughts, we free up energy to concentrate on important areas of our life — such as our passions and significant relationships. This is how we can find meaning and live our lives successfully.

Feel More

Today, we are in a fragmented world living our lives according to thinking rather than feeling. Both, thinking and feeling needed for a healthy balanced life. But, when people go about their thinking I mean only rationality then there arises the problem of exclusion. Today people are pushed to the periphery, marginalized, oppressed, suppressed and excluded because the feeling is missing among human beings.

Morrie beautifully explained and given more importance to the feeling that “Sometimes you cannot believe what you see, you have to believe what you feel. And if you are ever going to have other people trust you, you must feel that you can trust them, too—even when you’re in the dark. Even when you’re falling.”

It takes courage to trust others. Having faith in our intuition allows us to take bigger risks in relationships.

Living, and dying, on our own terms

Morrie encourages us to be ourselves, no holds barred: “Accept who you are; and revel in it.” He also invites us to devote ourselves to relationships with people who make us better. When we accept our very self then we will start living life on our own terms. Otherwise, in course of time, we lose our identity, originality and our authentic natural purity which is equal to dying not on our own term but on others identity.

Forgiveness and Self-Compassion

When the question about forgiveness was asked to Morrie he said “It’s not just other people we need to forgive. We also need to forgive ourselves.” We should forgive ourselves for all the things we didn’t do and all things we should have done. Self-compassion is very much interconnected with self-forgiveness. In order to forgive oneself, one must first experience self-compassion.

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Love

Morrie explains why people are so drawn to an excess of material things: People are trying to fill a hole that is not being filled by love. He asserts

that no amount of material goods will fill that hole, which is why people constantly think they need more possessions. He blames society for “brainwashing” people into believing that material things serve as an adequate substitute for love. In fact, the larger society has reduced love to love of the material things, forgetting the depth dimension of love, including the suffering that is necessarily part of it.

Regrets

Albom asked Morrie that whether he regrets the nearing culmination of his life on earth. Morrie responds with a lesson on how the culture doesn't encourage people to think about death and regrets until they are nearing their dying day. While they are living, he says, they are concerned about egotistical things, but they should constantly stand back and assess their life to determine what is there and what is missing from it. When we learn to accept the very nature and essence of human beings, we will be ready to accept anything that is coming in the path of our lives. Humankind is moving towards death from the moment of birth. Death is inevitable. Therefore, we must accept it. Otherwise, we will be regretting and feeling sad about our culmination (or elimination) on this earth.

Feeling Sorry

Albom asked Morrie whether he feels sorry for himself. Morrie answered that at times, he does, usually in the mornings. He often mourns for his body and the control that he has lost, and cries if he needs to. Afterwards, however, Morrie moves on and recognizes how lucky he is to have time to say goodbye to his loved ones before he dies. He consciously limits the amount of time he spends pitying himself, as he knows he must enjoy the little life he has left. The answer of Morrie is enriching and encountering. He just meant that life is with up and downs and falls and pits, happiness and sadness, suffering and death. Life

is of a two-sided coin. Happiness and suffering are inevitable and they are intertwined, interconnected. We must be aware of this. We are happy when something good happened to us. In the same way, we must understand that there is the possibility of suffering on the way of our lives. Therefore, we should learn to accept and take sufficient efforts to get rid of the problems. Morrie's very enriching answer is "he called himself lucky when he must endure such suffering. He says that he must enjoy the little life he has left rather than feeling sorry for his condition.

Culture

Each person must not simply accept the larger modern culture, which Morrie consistently critiques. He takes issue with modern culture's overvaluing of materiality, achievement, and superficial things, which he believes is not conducive to living a happy, fulfilled, and successful life. He instead advocates for the creation of personal cultures, or a system of living life that allows someone to be fulfilled through careful questioning of modern culture and religion. Throughout the Tuesday visits, he counsels his student Alбом to create his own personal culture so

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he too can live his life to the fullest. We, the people of the

21st century must create our own personal valuable culture devoid of materiality and superficial things. Today the modern culture is of modern technology. Humanity fell prey to the hands of modern technologies. Humanity is enslaved to modern technology. As result, we find happiness in the perishable things of technology. The happiness that is given by material things are not long-lasting. In order to be happy and live our life meaningfully, we must create our own personal valuable culture with our personal convictions so that we can live our lives to the fullest level of our existence on earth.

Marriage: “Love each other or perish.”

Morrie and his student talked about the culture’s problems with commitment, and the question was why most of the married relationships were not able to last forever? Morrie says that marriage is important, but also that since people don’t know themselves, they don’t know who they want to be with. He says that a loved one is important, as they will always be there for you for better or worse. Morrie says that the most important thing in a marriage is to have respect, be able to compromise, be open, have some common values, and believe in the marriage. He concludes by saying “Love each other or perish.”

Today marriage has become a problematic phenomenon. We see innumerable marriage bonds are broken in our lives. The reason for it is that people marry based on conditions rather than love, open talk, respect, compromise and convictions. They don’t know who they want to be with. When a marriage takes place without love, respect, open talk and conviction then it is proven to

When marriage takes place without love, respect, open talk and conviction then it is proven to broken. Therefore, Morrie beautifully says that marriage should have respect, compromise, open talk and common values.

broken. Therefore, Morrie beautifully says that marriage should have respect, compromise, open talk and common values.

A Critical Look

In this book, Morrie dealt with existential realities to make life more valuable and meaning full in the light of happiness through his chat with his own student Albom. The essence of this book is how can human persons become more valuable, meaningful with happiness? Morrie has very much dealt with the realities of our everyday lives. Some of the existential realities he deals with are love, self, compassion, culture, marriage, regrets, forgiveness, grief, suffering, happiness and death. When Morrie talked about love with his student Morrie, he said that modern human beings are brainwashed that material goods are substitutes for love. They are brainwashed and as a result of such brainwashing, human beings started believing it and finding love in material things. In this regard, I remember an incident that a woman was caring for her one-year-old child as well as mobile. Unfortunately, the mobile slipped from her hand and she left the child as well to catch the mobile. This shows how material became more valuable, meaningful than human beings in the postmodern age.

Morrie has very much dealt with the realities of our everyday lives. Some of the existential realities he deals with are: love, self, compassion, culture, marriage, regrets, forgiveness, grief, suffering, happiness and death.

We also read and hear a lot of things that people are murdered for the materials. This shows that love has lost its essence. Love on materials is increasing day by day. People

are after them. Morrie says that material possessions are not going to fulfil the thirst for love. Today we have to love people rather than things. When we do it with the help of Morrie's thoughts in our lives then we can reap the fruits of love in our lives with happiness. When Morrie spoke about the culture he said with grief that modern culture is overvaluing materiality, achievement, and superficial things. Morrie says that this is not conducive to a successful happy life. Modern technology is enslaving humanity. To come out of such a problem, we must create our own personal values and culture with our own personal convictions. Morrie says that the most important thing in a marriage is to have respect, be able to compromise, be open, have some common values, and believe in the marriage. Today marriages are mostly divorced because of the lack of conviction, love, open talk, compromise and common values. Morrie talked about death too. When Albom asked him whether he has negation or regret towards death, Morrie simply said that he is ready for anything. The culture somehow created a negation, hatred feeling among the people about the death. But, everyone must understand that death is part and parcel of our life. Death is inevitable. The culmination of the birth is death. The man from the moment of his birth walks towards death. Therefore, learn to accept the very nature and essence of existence to be devoid of regrets and to be with long-lasting happiness. Morrie encourages us to be ourselves, no holds barred: "Accept who you are; and revel in it." He also invites us to devote ourselves to relationships with people who make us better. When we accept our very self then we will start living life on our own terms. Otherwise, in course of time, we lose our identity, originality and our authentic natural purity which is equal to dying not on our own term but on others identity. What all Morrie spoke about is present in our own selves. The thing is, we must actualize them to live a life of value, meaning and happiness.

Conclusion

I would conclude this review with the citation from the Tamas Book that “The world is basically a paradoxical place”. It is both good and bad. But we experience much of evil in this world. This is the current scenario of the world. The interconnectivity between human persons has been lost. As a result, we experience a lot of evil things such as anguish, hatred feelings, jealousy and envy. When we live our lives with the thoughts of Morrie, I am sure that we will experience many good things in our lives rather than evil things.

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Suffering and the Emergence of Meaning in Life

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Abstract: Philosophers, psychologists and neuroscientists pose deep and difficult questions about pain and suffering and try to provide answers to these questions: What is pain? Is pain in the brain? Is there meaning in suffering? What makes pain unpleasant? This article provides a rich and wide-ranging exploration of these questions and offers important new insights into the philosophy of pain. To complement the author's reflection on pain, suffering and the emergence of meaning in life, he has gathered information about the said topic from various sources that could enrich the article and have reflected some concepts that help us understand the topic better.

Keywords: Suffering and Pain, Meaning in Suffering, Nobility in Suffering, The Philosophy of Pain, Pain as Beyond the Physical Injury, Pain is in the Brain, Pain and Punishment

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“Pain demands to be felt” John Green (From the Novel, *The Fault in Our Star*)

“Suffering is to feel hurt; it hurts you, incapacitates your body and keeps you from living normally.” (Cocks, 2017)

Introduction

Pain and suffering are very much part of everyone’s story. It is the part and parcel of our life. Suffering is universal. Pain has a long and venerable history from the time immemorial there has been suffering in the fallen World. Looking through the lens of a Christian Scripture, there is pain in the world because we are deprived of the perfectly blissful Godly Paradise due to our original sin and we are compelled to live in a *fallen World*. Thus, suffering was

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considered a punishment from God and we could hear God’s words re-echoing in our ears. “*By the sweat of your brow, you will eat your food*” (Genesis 3:19.) The origin of many pains ranging from mild and momentary to severe and prolonged, are identifiable cause, often external sometimes as an outcome of our action rather than a purely exogenous event. It can be so intimidating to face pain especially if that’s what one is trying to avoid having the whole time. But the good news is that pain is temporary, there is remedy for pain and can be meaningful.

Nowadays, pain and suffering have received increasing attention as philosophers, psychologists, and neuroscientists try to answer deep and difficult questions about it. What is pain? Is pain only a tissue damage? Is there a nobility in suffering? Does suffering have a meaning? What makes pain unpleasant? Is pain

only in the brain? How is pain related to the emotions? This article provides a rich and wide-ranging exploration of these questions and offer important new insights into the philosophy of pain. The article is divided into clear sections – What is pain? The Nature of Pain, Suffering and Pain, Modelling Pain in Philosophy, Modelling Pain in Psychology, Modelling Pain in Neuroscience and Modelling Pain in Ethics. Though the title of the article is “Suffering and the Emergence of Meaning in Life” and despite distinguishing between pain and suffering, I have used these two words interchangeably. I have done my research on in pain exclusively pertaining to human beings.

Understanding Pain?

A good place to begin is with the definition of pain proffered by the International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP in 1979): “An unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage, or described in terms of such damage.” (Murat, 2019)

Despite its ambiguity and subjectivity, we have seen the objective definition of pain by IASP in 1979. It must be noted that the validity of its definition has been challenged and a new definition has been suggested. As obvious IASP’s definition of pain encompasses both sensory

Pain may be considered as “An unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage, or described in terms of such damage.”

and emotional aspects of pain it does not include ‘hurt-feelings’ or ‘broken heart’ or ‘feeling of loneliness.’ The

definition focusses much on physical pain due to “tissue damage” but it in fact emotional pain could be more excruciating. Thus, the definition betrays the actual meaning of pain. No definition embraces all that it wishes to embrace and this is true in this regard too.

The etymology of the word ‘pain’ comes from the Latin root *poena*, meaning ‘penalty’ or ‘punishment’. Romance languages use versions of the Latin *dolor* to talk about pain. The English word ‘pain’ originally referred to punishment or penalty for an offence, also meant an unpleasant bodily sensation and mental or emotional suffering. We still use the phrase ‘on pain of death’ to refer to capital punishment. But, in the past, pain meant punishment, and lawful punishments frequently involved the deliberate infliction of bodily pain. (Grant, 2017) But today deliberate infliction of pain even if it is sanctioned by the state is totally irrelevant. Many countries have now done away with the capital punishment.

The Nature of Pain

Pain is a peculiar and weird phenomenon. There could be feeling of pain even when there is no visible injury or a ‘tissue damage’. “The pain in our left shoulder could be due to a shoulder injury, but it could also be a heart attack, in which case our pain is being referred from the chest to another location. Intuitively, we perhaps think that the pain is in our hearts – that is where the tissue damage is – but the sensation of pain locates the dysfunction in our shoulder. We are probably familiar by now with instances of phantom limb pain, an extreme example of this case. Folks missing a limb, an arm or a leg, often feel pain that seems to be located in the missing extremity. Obviously, there is no limb there, but the felt pain seems real nonetheless. It isn’t a delusion.” (Corns, 2017, p.19) One is not guaranteed to feel pain just because he got his finger cut (Leper,

for example) nor does she feel the pain because she got her tissue damaged (injury on a paralyzed had, for instance).

Pain and suffering cannot be treated exclusively in naturalistic, scientific terms, at least under a certain view of what science is. Medicine became a science at the end of the eighteenth century with the emergence of clinical, evidence-based medicine.

Suffering and Pain

Leper and paralyzed people may not have pain because they got their fingers amputated but that does not mean they are not suffering. In fact, we actually suffer the pain. They could suffer the loss of their fingers. This is a simple way of distinguishing between Suffering and Pain. While suffering could be mental and emotional, pain could be referred to as the physical pain. However, the effect of this two is one and the same - it “incapacitates your body and keeps you from living normally” (Cocks, 2017) Pain and suffering are one within the other. There is pain in suffering and there is suffering in pain.

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Sometimes the words “pain” and “suffering” are used synonymously, but the experience of pain has been differentiated from suffering. Suffering is referred to as indulging in the experience of pain but as also including vulnerability, dehumanization, a lost sense of self, lack of control over time and space, and an inability to find meaning or purpose in the painful experience.

Suffering is referred to as indulging in the experience of pain but as also including vulnerability, dehumanization, a lost sense of self, lack of control over time and space, and an inability to find meaning or purpose in the painful experience. In short, the term “suffering” attempts to convey the experience of pain beyond sensory attributes. In this accepted, I have used the term pain and suffering interchangeably.

Modelling Pain in Philosophy

The concept of Pain and the very act of pain itself puzzles philosopher who want to comprehend the true nature of pain. The very fact that pain has a privacy of experience – I cannot see the pain of others who are suffering excruciating pain is one of the thought-provoking philosophical questions. Pain is both a sort of subjective experience, but also the object of our experience and this is what Philosophers want to sort out. For philosophers’ pain is something that is ‘there in the world’ very much part of our experience. Besides location, we also experience pains as having such properties as shape, spatial extent, intensity, temporal duration, as well as various qualitative features, such as those which differentiate burning pains from stinging pains, aching pains from smarting pains, jabbing pains from shocking pains, and so forth. (Corns, 2017)

Pain is very much part of me and it teaches me that I am existing. Descartes’ “I think, therefore I exist” (*cogito ergo sum*) could be enriched with “I suffer, therefore I exist” because the (feeling of) pain conveys my existence more than my thoughts. I become someone who suffers my pain therefore my existence is real. It also gives us information about our world, just as our (other) perceptual systems do. Philosophers are not only interested in finding out what pain is and what it is not. They speculate and question the very presence of pain and are keen on finding the answer to the problem of pain. Though Buddha was very much

a practical man he too went on to speculate what really causes pain and through enlightenment brought out spectacular answer to end the suffering, advising his disciples to follow the Four Noble Truths. “I teach suffering, its origin, cessation and path. That’s all I teach”, declared the Buddha 2500 years ago (cited by Hertenberg, 2019)

Modelling Pain in Psychology

”A man is not so much hurt by what happens as by his opinions of what happens” (Michel De Montaigne)

“Pain represents a complex psychological phenomenon that cannot be objectively measured nor directly observed”

Kate Naud believes that “Pain is so much easier to understand when we can see it. But pain is more than that.” It is obvious from our experiences too that there is pain even without a tissue damage (Migraine, for instance.) and the pain in the absence of tissue damage or disease is assigned to undefined “psychological reasons” (Williams, 2017: 143). Is pain an emotion or a sensation? This question is answered in the studies of pain from psychological perspective. “Pain represents a complex psychological phenomenon that cannot be objectively measured nor directly observed” (Hadjistavropoulos, 2017: 154).

In 1995 British Medical Journal published an astonishing report about a twenty-nine-year-old builder who accidentally stumped his foot on fifteen centimetres (15. cm) nail that pierced right through his boot. He was in such an agonising pain that even a slightest moment could cause him excruciating pain. But when the doctors took of his

boot, they were unbelievably surprised to see that the nail had never touched his foot at all but penetrated between the toes. (Williamson, 2017) Then the question is: What causes pain?

For so many years scientist thought that pain was a direct response to ‘tissue damage’ going by that logic the more severe the injury, the more pain it should cause. But as we learn more about science of pain, the pain and tissue damage do not always go hand in hand. Pain is experienced even without an injury like the builder. There are two phenomena at play; the experience of pain and the biological process called nociception. Nociceptors often referred to as “pain receptors,” are free nerve endings located all over the body, including the skin, muscles, joints, bones, and internal organs. They play a pivotal role in

For so many years scientist thought that pain was a direct response to ‘tissue damage’ going by that logic the more severe the injury, the more pain it should cause. But as we learn more about science of pain, the pain and tissue damage do not always go hand in hand. Pain is experienced even without an injury like the builder.

how we feel and react to pain. The main purpose of a nociceptor is to respond to damage to the body by transmitting signals to the spinal cord and brain. The brain at times produces pain if it decides that the body needs a protection. Psychological factors play a vital role in pain by influencing the nociceptors and by influencing the pain directly. A person’s emotional state, beliefs about pain, expectation about treatment and memories can influence how much pain he or she experience pain. Studies show that children those who believe they have control over pain experienced less pain than those who do not. (Pate, 2019) Another instance that helps us understand that pain is also psychical in nature is the Phantom limb pain, referring to

ongoing painful sensations that seem to be coming from the part of the limb that is no longer there. The limb is gone, but the pain is real.

Modelling Pain in Neuroscience

“Pain is defined as an unpleasant feeling that is conveyed to the brain by sensory neurons” (Farlex, 2016)

Last decade or two our understanding of brain mechanisms of pain has been revolutionised. Brain mechanisms involved in nociception and acute and chronic pain. Pain as we have discussed is subjectively perceived – direct experience. However, “a comprehensive scientific explanation of the Central Nervous System (CNS) processes that generate the subjective experience of pain still remains elusive...the question of how the brain generates the subjective experience of pain can be seen as the quintessential mind–body problem of how subjective experience arises from matter...Although pain

Pain is like a birth right we cannot avoid it is something that we have to struggle with throughout our life. However, it is humanly possible to make meaning out of it. Pain and suffering nourish us, they enlighten us and serve as a wakeup call. Acceptance of suffering not only alleviates the pain but also paves the way to the emergence of meaning out of it like a mother sacrifices and suffers for the good cause of her children.

cannot be ontologically reduced to any one state of neuronal activity, it may be causally reduced to neuronal activity... that all pain is caused by nociception.” (Roy and Wager,

2017) What they try to drive home is that pain is caused by the Central and Peripheral nervous system.

Neurologically speaking, pain is in the brain (not in the mind, because pain is real). Studies have shown that pain changes the brain functionally, structurally and chemically which they term it as “centralization of pain.” According to David Borsook, “Chronic pain induces abnormal function in brain circuits, including circuits involved in cognition, autonomic responses, and other more complex integrative behaviours (e.g., fear, anxiety, interoception, reward and aversion).” (Borsook, 2012) Pain is in the brain and the nervous system signals us that we need to take care of our body.

Conclusion

“Those who have a “WHY” to live, can bear with any “HOW” (Friederich Nietzsche)

According to Greek tragedy-drama there’s nobility in suffering. The three great playwrights of tragedy were Aeschylus, Sophocles, and Euripides and they produced such dramas that would evoke ‘pity and terror’ the tool that serves to purify the characters. This literary device, Aristotle called this experience, “*Catharsis*” – way of purifying. He argued that tragedy cleansed the heart through pity and terror, purging us of our petty concerns and worries by making us aware that there can be nobility in suffering. In Greek word, pain means penalty. Plato said that pain arises from within the body and indicating that pain is more of an emotional experience. This experience of pain and suffering purify us, they serve as a tool to awake us from our dormant state. And like the mother in pangs of giving birth they say suffers alot but that suffering becomes meaningful when the child is born, she forgets her suffering and rejoices in her new born baby. When we suffer for others, our suffering

becomes meaningful. In this light Christians understand their Scripture better. The passion of Christ to save humanity from the clutches of sin is an epitome of meaning in suffering. Christian saints like St. Alphonsa or St. Faustina had always offered their suffering for good of others thus finding meaning in their sufferings.

There is always *silver lining in the dark clouds*. At times there are pain and sufferings in life but they refresh us, and act as a wakeup call to be vigilant in life. Sometimes suffering also catapults us to heights from our lowly state. Suffering really makes us come in touch with ourselves. It also illumines us and we begin to reflect, contemplate and try to find our own answers to live good life. We understand that suffering is real and therefore we keep ourselves agile to avert the sufferings in the future. Pain and suffering are a constant reminder for us to take care of our body. “Pain is bearable if we know it will end not if we deny it exists,” affirms Victor Frankl

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Knowledge as/and Experience

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Abstract: Knowledge is a key constituent in building up a better personality. What I know is crucial in making what I am. This gorgeous resource has immensely helped human kind to fuel for their innovations. Hence knowledge acquisition is recognised as an inescapable commitment. John Locke, the famous British empiricist argues that knowledge is acquired through experiences. He claims, ‘No man’s knowledge goes beyond his experience’. Experiencing different situations play a vital role to demarcate between what to do and what not. But is ‘Experience’ an only exclusive way to knowledge? Is there only a solitary approach to knowledge acquisition? This essay will help us understand the significance, limitations and applicability of this insight.

Keywords: Knowledge and Experience, Empiricism, A Priori and a Posteriori Knowledge, Tabula Rasa

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Introduction

Knowledge is a highly valued state in which a person is in cognitive contact with reality (Zagzebski, 2017). From Womb to Tomb and Tip to toe, human like to identify themselves as seekers of knowledge. Perhaps this acknowledgement may have helped humans to distinct themselves from other species and rather honoured them to rule the whole earth. But how come this gorgeous resource reserved solely for humans? The credit goes to the highly complex nervous system that served human to develop a unique capability to extract abstract ideas from concrete experiences. The better understanding of this mechanism may have helped British empiricist John Locke to make his famous claim, “No man’s knowledge can go beyond his experience” (Locke, 1690).

Empiricists search for evidence that are unearthed through experiments or sense experiences. They reject any importance give to a priori information and admired the significance given to a posteriori knowledge.

Empiricism, a philosophical theory, states that knowledge comes only through sense experience. (Psillos et al, 2010). Empiricists search for evidence that are unearthed through experiments or sense experiences. They reject any importance given to a priori information and admired the significance given to a posteriori knowledge. As an empiricist himself, Locke too gave a direct and rather strong relationship between Knowledge and experience. But it seems that Locke and the other empiricists had unknowingly constricted the scope of knowledge exclusively with experiences. Even if knowledge comes primarily through experiences, we must not forget the other approaches towards the same.

John Locke

John Locke is an English philosopher and the first of British empiricist. His ideas influenced the development of epistemology and political philosophy and he is regarded as one of the most influential early and enlightenment thinkers. He inspired the American and French revolution. He argues that all of our Ideas are ultimately derived from the experience and knowledge of which we are capable of, is there for severely limited in its scope and certainty. His most famous works are ‘An essay concerning human understanding’ (Locke, 1690) and ‘Two treatises of government’ (Locke, 1689). He is often referred to as philosopher of freedom or father of philosophy.

The Significance of the Insight

Locke truly believed that knowledge is shaped by experiences. To support his view, he claims that the human mind at birth is like a ‘tabula rasa’. ‘Tabula rasa’ or ‘blank slate’ is a philosophical concept that argues that the human mind is like an empty slate at birth, and later it gets filled with ideas through experiences (Erhard 2001). No tide has fallen back without kissing the shore. The analogy fits perfectly when defining Locke’s quote. Whatever situation we go through, makes portraits in our mind.

Locke claims that human mind at birth is like a ‘tabula rasa’. ‘Tabula rasa’ or ‘blank slate’ is a philosophical concept that argues that human mind is like an empty slate at birth, and later it gets filled with ideas through experiences

This will then resurrects in near future as ideas and thoughts. Without seeing, smelling, feeling or hearing human cannot learn anything. For example, only through the experience we can know that flame can burn and cause harm. The statement disregards the existence of a Priori knowledge and sticks to the fact that is obtained by reasoning, which is justified by truth.

The empirical knowledge or a posteriori knowledge have really helped mankind to fuel up our majestic innovations. When the archaic men witnessed an accidental fire in the forest, he learned about the source of light, warmth, weapon against ferocious animals and an energy to cook. Then they began to use fire on daily basis and domestication of fire became a significant step on their way to the hegemonic position and wide innovations (Harari, 2015). Therein, every situation they confronted, harnessed immense knowledge from them. This led the transfiguration of the archaic to the modern humans. Hence, soundly these facts stress that Locke's quote worked well with humans.

Application for Our Times

Our senses are our primary sources of knowledge. What I see, hear, experience and all will play a huge role in explaining what I am. To cast a good individual, we need to provide them with better experiences. 'For of thorns men do not gather figs, nor of a bramble bush gather they grapes. Good casts good, while evil casts evil' (English Standard Version Bible, 2009). The Environment we are brought up overwhelmingly plays an inevitable role in determining our character. What I know and experience is reflected in what I am.

In our present scenario, Locke's words have significant application. A child is learning through experiences. In the developmental stages of a baby child, there is infallible evidence from biological and behavioural sciences that gene activity interacts with events and experiences she receives (Carlson, 2005). The abstract ideas are extracted to the child's minds through concrete experiences. The house, classroom conditions, teachers, surrounding and all the circumstances child encounter, is his experience of the world. Deliberately, if better experience are made to coincided in a child's life, he/she can be very well mould into better personality.

In the developmental stages of a baby child, there is infallible evidence from biological and behavioural sciences that gene activity interacts with events and experiences she receives.

My Take

Many people consider old people as wise because they have learned from good and bad experiences throughout their lives. Learning from experiences are the significant source of knowledge for us. Therefore, Locke's quote has an important application in our life. But still, we cannot assert our knowledge should be an exact reflection of our experience because there are other facts beyond our experiences. For example; I believe in the existence of God and I'm sure that he created everything but still I cannot empirically prove my belief is right or wrong. My knowledge and love of God is not from my experience, but beyond it and has an important role in making my life. Hence there are some facts that lay beyond our experiences. Our knowledge, therefore, should also consider the pre-existing beliefs, faiths, intuition, authority (include parents, doctors, teachers, priests, etc.) and other notions that our ancestors have preserved for us. We cannot instantaneously reject the

glimpses of truths in them for the simple reason for not experiencing it.

The quote also may feel like knowledge being constrained to experience alone. Locke seems to take an exclusive path to knowledge. But let us not forget other sub streams towards the same. Being little exposed to experiences, young minds will find it difficult to seek knowledge when stubbornly stick to experience alone. Therefore, in the present scenario, it is witless to stick on to experience alone as a source of knowledge. The competitive world surpasses all those who stick to one source of knowledge. A true seeker of knowledge must have access to all doors (of knowledge).

Being little exposed to experiences, young minds will find it difficult to seek knowledge when stubbornly stick to experience alone. Therefore, in the present scenario, it is witless to stick on to experience alone as a source of knowledge.

Conclusion

Knowledge is a significant factor in building our life better. To grow in our career, we need to acquire as much as knowledge as possible. Locke's insight seem to work very well with archaic humans but when considering the present scenario, relying to experience alone will certainly limit our access to knowledge. Also young minds will too will struggle because they are less exposed to experiences. The knowledge gained through reasons and reflections may be the best but let us also consider other approaches of knowledge too. As knowledge is too wide, relying on one approach alone will not do good to move further forward. Try to seek knowledge from whatever ways we can and stop not until and unless we 'kick the bucket'.

The knowledge gained through reasons and reflections may be the best but let us also consider other approaches of knowledge too. As knowledge is too wide, relying on one approach alone will not do good to move further forward. Try to seek knowledge from whatever ways we can and stop not until and unless we 'kick the bucket'.

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